

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

Deliverable title	Report on the evaluation of atmospheric blocking and underlying mechanisms in the SR-ESMs
Deliverable number	D46 (Del. Rel. No. D9.1)
Planned delivery date	31/07/2025
Actual date of issue	16/07/2025
Nature of deliverable	Report
Lead partner	UBERN
Dissemination level	Public

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programmes under grant agreement No 101003470

About this document

The report summarizes how well atmospheric blocking, in terms of frequency and persistence, is represented in the SR-ESMs and as compared to CMIP6 model.

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WP9

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Executive summary

Atmospheric blocking is a key driver of midlatitude weather extremes, including heatwaves and cold spells. However, current global climate models (GCMs) struggle to accurately simulate blocking frequency, persistence, and spatial distribution. This study evaluates atmospheric blocking in the next generation of storm-resolving Earth system models developed within the nextGEMS project. We analyse blocking in simulations run with the ICON and IFS-FESOM models operating at 10 km atmospheric resolution coupled to a 5 km ocean.

We assess blocking frequency, duration, and size using 30-year historical simulations, comparing the storm-resolving models to the ERA5 reanalysis and to a CMIP6 multi-model ensemble. Results show that storm-resolving simulations—particularly IFS have the potential to improve the representation of blocking, together with more realistic jets and storm tracks, reduced biases in block size and persistence, and improved blocking frequency patterns over the North Atlantic and North Pacific given good lower boundary conditions. Atmosphere-only experiments (IFS AMIP) highlight the critical role of SST forcing and ocean–atmosphere coupling in controlling blocking variability. Analysis of projected changes under SSP3-7.0 scenarios indicates a redistribution of blocking activity under future warming, with model differences reflecting sensitivities to background flow, SST anomalies, and moist processes. Despite notable advances, biases remain, linked the coupling to the ocean and likely uncertainties in the representation of diabatic processes. Overall, our results demonstrate that storm-resolving models offer the potential for improvements over coarser GCMs for simulating blocking dynamics.

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Objectives

Project objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following specific project topics.

The table below outlines the overarching objectives of the nextGEMS. Objectives that the work for the current deliverable contributes to are marked with *yes*.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	no
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	yes
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	yes
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | no |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | no |

Work package objectives

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package as indicated below.

Objectives of WP9	Relevance in this deliverable?
Investigate whether resolving the storm-scale variability in weather systems and in the land surface, together with their consistent interactions with the larger scales, affects the climatology of blocking, the statistics of dry and warm spells, the mean surface radiation balance as well as near-term changes in aggregated temperature and precipitation statistics (O2)	yes
Quantify the carbon stocks and fluxes over Europe at storm-resolving resolution and compare these estimates to ones from current ESMs (O2)	no
Use the production runs to reassess solar power on the global scale and to produce global maps of hazardous weather at unprecedented resolution (O3)	no

Synergies

The analysis presented in this deliverable complements the findings of Deliverable 9.2, which focuses on the simulation of warm and dry spells in the nextGEMS models. Atmospheric blocking plays a key role in the development and persistence of such extremes, and our assessment of blocking dynamics, frequency, and persistence provides critical insight into their dynamical drivers. In particular, the projected changes in blocking frequency and spatial distribution under SSP3-7.0, such as the reduction of North Atlantic blocking in IFS, help explain trends in dry spell characteristics over Southern Europe highlighted in D9.2. Conversely, SST-related biases that affect blocking in IFS could also impact projections of future heatwave and drought risks.

This work contributes to the overall project goals by:

- Addressing **Objective O1(ii)** through a systematic evaluation of storm-resolving model (SRM) climate projections, particularly in terms of their ability to simulate persistent large-scale circulation features such as blocking.
- Supporting **Objective O2(iv)** by assessing storm-scale variability and its coupling with large-scale atmospheric dynamics in the extra-tropics.

Together, Deliverables 9.1 and 9.2 demonstrate the added value of storm-resolving models for understanding compound extreme events and their underlying dynamical processes in a changing climate.

1 Introduction

Extratropical cyclones and atmospheric blocking are key drivers of midlatitude weather variability. While extratropical cyclones are fast-moving low-pressure systems that bring stormy conditions, atmospheric blocking refers to quasi-stationary, long-lived high-pressure systems that disrupt the typical west-to-east flow of weather systems (Elliott and Smith, 1949; Rex, 1950; Namias, 1964). By persistently deflecting storm tracks, blocking can maintain extreme conditions such as prolonged heatwaves in summer or cold spells in winter (e.g., Kautz et al., 2022). These events have severe socio-economic impacts, affecting sectors like energy production, agriculture, and public health, making their accurate simulation a priority for climate modeling (e.g., Planchon et al., 2015; Grams et al., 2017; Ormanova et al., 2020).

Despite their importance, CMIP5 and CMIP6 global climate models (GCMs) struggle to reproduce key characteristics of blocking, including its frequency, location, and duration (e.g., Schiemann et al., 2017; Schiemann et al., 2020). CMIP6 models, in particular, continue to underestimate blocking frequency in critical regions such as the Euro-Atlantic sector (Dolores-Tesillos et al., 2025). These biases degrade the skill of climate projections, especially regarding the persistence of high-impact weather regimes (Davini and D’Andrea, 2016). Several factors contribute to these deficiencies, including coarse horizontal resolution, inadequate storm-track representation, and simplified parameterizations of moist diabatic processes (Woollings et al., 2018).

Sea surface temperature (SST) biases have been identified as a key factor contributing to blocking frequency biases (Scaife et al., 2011). In particular, a negative SST bias south of Greenland is found in several climate models (Scaife et al., 2011; Athanasiadis et al., 2022). This colder ocean surface enhances the low-level temperature gradient, leading to stronger low-level baroclinicity and reduced surface evaporation (Scaife et al., 2011; Athanasiadis et al., 2022; Cheung et al., 2023). The occurrence of blocking events during the 2005/2006 European winter was shown to be sensitive to, and significantly influenced by, warm surface temperature anomalies upstream over the western Atlantic Ocean and North America (Crocì-Maspoli and Davies, 2009). Additionally, blocking frequency has been found to be sensitive to tropical SST biases (e.g., Hinton et al., 2009). The ocean-atmosphere feedback is also evident on longer timescales: for instance, the wind forcing associated with blocked regimes weakens ocean gyres and reduces heat exchange, both of which contribute to the warm phase of Atlantic multidecadal variability (AMV) (Häkkinen et al., 2011).

Furthermore, moist processes—such as latent heat release associated with condensation and warm conveyor belts—are increasingly recognized as essential for blocking onset and maintenance (Steinfeld and Pfahl, 2019; Steinfeld et al., 2020; Dolores-Tesillos et al., 2025). Their role for mid-latitude dynamics is expected to grow in a warming climate, yet they remain poorly resolved or parameterized in most climate models.

Recent efforts suggest that increasing climate model resolution can improve blocking representation by better resolving the orography, warm conveyor belts, jet structure, and transient eddies (Willison et al., 2013; Schemm, 2023; De Luca et al., 2024). However, the interactions between model resolution, ocean forcing, dry dynamical processes (e.g., storm tracks), and moist processes remain poorly understood.

This study investigates atmospheric blocking in the Northern Hemisphere using storm-resolving simulations from the nextGEMS project. We analyze control, historical and SSP3-7.0 simulations with the Integrated Forecasting System coupled to the Finite-volume Sea ice-Ocean Model (IFS-FESOM) and the ICOSahedral Non-hydrostatic model (ICON), comparing them against ERA5 and CMIP6 models. We assess the influence of model resolution, ocean forcing, and large-scale dynamics on blocking characteristics during both winter and summer.

We aim to answer the following research questions:

- How does model resolution influence atmospheric blocking frequency, duration, and size?
- What is the role of the background flow, the ocean forcing, and the storm-track activity for biases in blocking representation in km-scale models?

We also discuss the potential role of moist processes, such as warm conveyor belts and diabatic heating, in contributing to remaining biases in storm-resolving models, and highlight them as a priority for future research.

This report is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the data sources and simulation setup. Section 3 presents the methodology used for identifying and characterizing blocking events, and capturing the storm track activity. The main results are presented in Section 4, followed by a discussion of the key findings in Section 5. Finally, Section 6 summarizes the conclusions and outlines future research directions.

2 Data

The main data source is the nextGEMS project (Segura et al., 2025), which has developed a new generation of global storm-resolving Earth system models. The first modelling cycle included simulations with the ICOSahedral Non-hydrostatic model (ICON) and the Integrated Forecasting System coupled to the Finite-volume Sea ice-Ocean Model (IFS-FESOM) as described by Hohenegger et al., 2023 and Rackow et al., 2025, respectively. All simulation data are publicly available via the World Data Center for Climate (Koldunov et al., 2023; Wieners et al., 2024). Table 3 provides an overview of all the simulations analyzed in this study, which are primarily derived from storm-resolving modeling efforts.

The nextGEMS models—ICON and IFS-FESOM are fully coupled models (atmosphere, ocean, sea ice, and land) at storm-resolving resolution. Although capable of including additional components such as the carbon cycle and aerosols, the simulations used in this study were performed without these Earth system extensions. Therefore, we refer to ICON and IFS-FESOM as storm-resolving Earth system models, consistent with the terminology in Segura et al., 2025.

In addition to the nextGEMS simulations, we analyze an atmosphere-only IFS simulation (IFS AMIP) from the European Eddy-Rich Earth-System Models (EERIE) project (<https://eerie-project.eu/>). The EERIE project aims to assess the role of ocean mesoscale processes in modulating climate variability from seasonal to centennial scales. The IFS AMIP simulation follows a configuration similar to the IFS-FESOM setup but is forced with prescribed sea surface temperatures (SSTs) and sea ice concentrations (SICs) based on observations (e.g., Gates et al.,

1999; Eyring et al., 2016; Ackerley et al., 2018). This configuration is particularly useful for isolating the impact of air–sea coupling on the large-scale atmospheric circulation (e.g., Priestley et al., 2023).

We also include a historical ICON simulation from the Climate Change Adaptation Digital Twin of the Destination Earth initiative (<https://destination-earth.eu>). This initiative aims to develop operational, multi-decadal, storm-resolving simulations to support climate change impact assessments and adaptation planning at local to regional scales (Hoffmann et al., 2023; Sandu, 2024).

In terms of simulation periods and forcings, the IFS control or “perpetual” runs (IFS 4.4 km and IFS 28 km) were integrated over five years using fixed 2020 conditions as forcing. Historical simulations (ICON hist, IFS hist) cover the period from 1990 to 2019 and follow the CMIP6 historical forcing protocol. Future simulations (ICON fut, IFS fut), also referred to as “production runs,” span 2020 to 2049 and use greenhouse gas concentrations—including ozone—prescribed by the CMIP6 SSP3-7.0 scenario (O’Neill et al., 2016).

The ability of the nextGEMS simulations to reproduce large-scale circulation patterns is evaluated against ERA5 reanalysis data (Hersbach et al., 2020) for the period 1990–2019. To contextualize the performance of storm-resolving models within the broader climate modeling landscape, we additionally analyze simulations from eight CMIP6 global climate models (see Table 4), which cover the historical period 1985–2014 and were used in the study by Dolores-Tesillos et al., 2025. For consistency across datasets, all relevant variables are remapped to a common $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ spatial resolution. Note, that most of the multidecadal simulations consider 30 years. As Gao et al., 2025 discuss 30 years of simulation are enough to capture the variability and identify robust blocking signatures.

Model	Δx_A (km)	Δx_O (km)	Period	Forcing
IFS 4.4km	4.4	5	5 years	Perpetual
IFS 28km	28	25	5 years	Perpetual
IFS AMIP	9	5	30 years	Observed SST/SIC
IFS hist	9	5	30 years	Historical (CMIP6)
IFS SSP3-7.0	9	5	30 years	SSP3-7.0
ICON hist	10	5	25 years	Historical (CMIP6)
ICON SSP3-7.0	10	5	25 years	SSP3-7.0

Table 3: Overview of nextGEMS simulations performed with the ICON and IFS-FESOM (IFS) models. Δx_A and Δx_O denote the atmospheric and oceanic horizontal resolution, respectively. “Perpetual” refers to simulations driven by fixed 2020 conditions, while “Observed SST/SIC” refers to prescribed sea surface temperatures and sea ice concentrations based on observations.

Model	Δx_A (km)	Period	Forcing	Member ID
MRI-ESM2-0	100	30 years	Historical	r1i1p1f1
ACCESS-CM2	250	30 years	Historical	r1i1p1f1
EC-Earth3	100	30 years	Historical	r1i1p1f1
MPI-ESM1-2-HR**	100	30 years	Historical	r1i1p1f1
CESM2-WACCM*	100	30 years	Historical	r1i1p1f1
MIROC6	250	30 years	Historical	r1i1p1f1
MPI-ESM1-2-LR**	250	30 years	Historical	r1i1p1f1
CESM2*	100	30 years	Historical	r1i1p1f1

Table 4: List of CMIP6 models used in this study, including their horizontal resolution (Δx_A), simulation period, forcing, and member ID. Models marked with * or ** share components or dependencies, as discussed in Brunner et al., 2020. The member ID encodes simulation variants based on realization, initialization, physics, and forcing configuration (e.g., r2i1p3f222).

3 Methods

3.1 Blocking identification and tracking

Anomaly-based index (ANOM). The ANOM index is calculated following the approach of Woollings et al. (2018) and similar to earlier studies (e.g., Schwierz et al., 2004). It identifies blocking by tracking anomalies in the 500 hPa geopotential height field (Z500). The methodology consists of the following steps:

- A 31-day running mean is applied to the daily Z500 data over each decadal baseline period (e.g., 1990–1999, 2000–2009, and 2010–2019). This step removes interannual variability and long-term trends. A daily climatology is then computed as the mean Z500 for each calendar day across the corresponding decade.
- Anomalies are obtained by subtracting the decadal climatology from the corresponding daily Z500 values.
- To remove high-frequency variability, the anomaly fields are smoothed using a 2-day running mean. A blocking threshold is then determined as the 90th percentile of Z500 anomalies over the 50–80°N latitude band.
- Candidate blocking events are identified when the anomaly exceeds this threshold. These events must also satisfy a persistent and quasi-stationarity criterion: a spatial overlap of at least 50% between consecutive days for a minimum of 5 days (persistence criterion).

Absolute index (ABS). Instantaneous blocks (IBs) are identified based on reversals in the meridional geopotential height gradient, following the method of Brunner and Steiner (2017) and consistent with previous work (e.g., Dole and Gordon, 1983; Tibaldi and Molteni, 1990; Scherrer et al., 2006; Davini et al., 2012; Davini and D’Andrea, 2016; Rohrer et al., 2018; Rohrer et al., 2019; Dolores-Tesillos et al., 2025). Three gradients are computed at each longitude λ and central latitude ϕ :

$$\Delta Z_N(\lambda, \phi) = \frac{Z(\lambda, \phi + \Delta\phi) - Z(\lambda, \phi)}{\Delta\phi} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta Z_S(\lambda, \phi) = \frac{Z(\lambda, \phi - \Delta\phi) - Z(\lambda, \phi)}{\Delta\phi} \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta Z_E(\lambda, \phi) = \frac{Z(\lambda, \phi - 2\Delta\phi) - Z(\lambda, \phi - \Delta\phi)}{\Delta\phi} \quad (3)$$

For the Northern Hemisphere, a grid point is classified as blocked if it satisfies the following conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta Z_N &< -10 \text{ m } (\text{°lat.}^{-1}) \\ \Delta Z_S &< 0 \text{ m } (\text{°lat.}^{-1}) \\ \Delta Z_E &> 5 \text{ m } (\text{°lat.}^{-1}) \end{aligned}$$

Here, λ denotes longitude (from 180°W to 179°E), and ϕ spans latitudes from 75°S to 75°N. Gradients are calculated using $\Delta\phi = 15^\circ$.

Following prior studies (e.g., Tibaldi and Molteni, 1990; Davini et al., 2012; Prodhomme et al., 2016; Davini and D’Andrea, 2020), we do not apply a temporal or spatial filtering to the instantaneous blocking field. This ensures a larger sample size and retains the detailed spatial patterns of blocking events. Notably, results remain qualitatively similar when filtering is applied, as discussed in Davini and D’Andrea (2020).

3.2 Blocking metrics

To characterize blocking events, we compute several metrics from the identified blocking fields. **Frequency** is defined as the number of blocked days per season or year at each grid point, providing spatial and temporal information on blocking occurrence. **Duration** refers to the total length of each blocking episode, while **size** denotes the spatial extent of the blocking pattern, calculated as the number of contiguous grid points meeting the blocking criteria on a given day. These metrics allow for a comprehensive comparison of blocking characteristics across models and scenarios. We present the analysis for the periods of December to February (DJF) and June to August (JJA).

3.3 Storm tracks

To quantify synoptic-scale weather variability, we apply a Lanczos bandpass filter (2–6 days) to daily geopotential height at 500 hPa (Hoskins and Hodges, 2002; Greeves et al., 2007; Davini et al., 2017). The resulting bandpass-filtered fields are denoted by a prime ($'$). Storm tracks are identified based on the standard deviation of the filtered geopotential height (Z'), which serves as a proxy for the intensity and location of transient eddies.

Storm track intensity is computed seasonally for boreal winter (DJF) and summer (JJA), providing insight into the spatial and temporal variability of synoptic activity across different models and time periods.

4 Results

4.1 Role of resolution in the IFS-FESOM simulations

We begin by comparing the blocking frequency and properties in different IFS-FESOM simulations (IFS 4.4 km, IFS 28 km, IFS hist) against five-year random samples from ERA5 data to assess the role of resolution in simulating blocking frequency and duration.

Figure 1 shows the seasonal blocking frequency in the Northern Hemisphere during boreal winter (DJF) and summer (JJA). During DJF (Figure 1 a,b,c and d), the highest-resolution simulation (IFS 4.4 km) exhibits a blocking frequency pattern that closely resembles ERA5 in the Pacific and North Atlantic basins. The lowest-resolution simulation overestimates blocking frequency over the Pacific. Interestingly, while increasing resolution improves the large-scale pattern over the Pacific, it also leads to an overestimation of blocking frequency over North America (Fig. 1b).

During JJA (Figure 1 e,f,g and h) the blocking frequency increases south of Greenland as resolution increases. For example, the IFS 4.4 km simulation overestimates blocking frequency in this region by nearly 80%, as indicated by the hatching in Fig. 1f.

To further assess the impact of resolution, Figures 2a,c shows the number of blocking events per year in ERA5 and IFS. During DJF, both the mean and median number of blocks improves with increasing resolution, indicating a clearer relationship between model resolution and blocking frequency in winter. In contrast, the JJA results reveal a more complex pattern: both the lowest and highest resolution simulations align more closely with ERA5, suggesting a non-linear relationship between resolution and summer blocking frequency.

Figures 2b,d display the distribution of blocking durations. They vary between a median value of 11 days in ERA5 and a median value of 6 days in the 4.4 km IFS simulation. In DJF the IFS 28 km run achieves a mean and median duration closest to ERA5. For JJA, the IFS 4.4 km simulation yields a median and mean duration closest to ERA5.

Figure 1: Northern Hemisphere Blocking frequency based on the ANOM index in a,e) ERA5 and in IFS simulations at b,f) 4.4 km, c,g) 9 km, and d,h) 28 km resolution during a,b,c,d) December–February and e,f,g,h) June–July. Hatched areas indicate regions where the bias relative to ERA5 exceeds 80%. Black dots mark regions where differences are statistically significant, based on bootstrapping with random 5-year samples from ERA5

Figure 2: Northern Hemisphere: Panels a and c show the number of blocking events per year, while panels b and d display the persistence (duration) of blocking events. The analysis covers the periods a–b) December to February and c–d) June to July. Boxes represent the interquartile range (Q1–Q3), with the horizontal line indicating the median. Whiskers extend from the 5th to the 95th percentile, and the red dot denotes the mean.

To provide a global perspective, we analyze blocking frequency and duration in the Southern Hemisphere (Figs. 3 and 4). Overall, the IFS simulations capture the primary blocking hotspot in the South Pacific Ocean as seen in ERA5.

During DJF, the coarser-resolution simulation is closest to ERA5 in terms of blocking frequency over the South Pacific, but it significantly overestimates blocking frequency over the South Atlantic and Indian Oceans (Fig. 3d). As resolution increases, this overestimation is reduced while maintaining the South Pacific as the main blocking hotspot. (Fig. 3b). A similar behavior is observed in JJA: blocking overestimation in the South Atlantic and Indian Oceans decreases with increasing resolution.

We further assess the SH model performance by examining the number of blocking events per year (Figs. 4a,c). ERA5 exhibits low interannual variability, likely due to the short 5-year evaluation period. Still, the simulations that best capture the mean and median number of blocks are those at higher resolution—IFS 9 km in DJF and IFS 4.4 km in JJA. Figures 4b,d show the distribution of blocking durations. The mean and median durations in the IFS 4.4 km simulation are similar to those in the IFS 28 km run.

Figure 3: Southern Hemisphere Blocking frequency based on the ANOM index in a,e) ERA5 and in IFS simulations at b,f) 4.4 km, c,g) 9 km, and d,h) 28 km resolution during a,b,c,d) December–February and e,f,g,h) June–July. Hatched areas indicate regions where the bias relative to ERA5 exceeds 80%. Black dots mark regions where differences are statistically significant, based on bootstrapping with random 5-year samples from ERA5.

Figure 4: Southern Hemisphere: Panels a and c show the number of blocking events per year, while panels b and d display the persistence (duration) of blocking events. The analysis covers the periods a–b) December to February and c–d) June to July. Boxes represent the interquartile range (Q1–Q3), with the horizontal line indicating the median. Whiskers extend from the 5th to the 95th percentile, and the red dot denotes the mean.

In general, we find that increasing horizontal resolution leads to regional improvements in the simulation of blocking frequency, particularly in the Northern Hemisphere across both seasons, and in the Southern Hemisphere during DJF. However, some regional biases persist even at high resolution, such as overestimated blocking over North America and south of Greenland, highlighting that resolution alone does not fully resolve all systematic errors.

It is important to note that blocking frequency exhibits substantial spatial and interannual variability. A significance test indicates that many of the apparent biases may be attributable to internal variability, as suggested by the stippling in Figs. 1 and 3.

In terms of blocking duration, some improvements with resolution are evident in the Northern Hemisphere during DJF. The IFS 4.4 km simulation better captures the observed variability in duration, while in the Southern Hemisphere, gains in duration metrics are more modest, with similar performance between the 4.4 km and 28 km simulations.

Taken together, these results suggest the potential added value of high-resolution simulations for capturing key characteristics of atmospheric blocking, consistent with previous studies (Schiemann et al., 2017; De Luca et al., 2024; Gao et al., 2025). To further investigate the origin of the remaining biases in storm-resolving simulations, we now turn to the multidecadal experiments. These longer simulations enable a more robust assessment of internal variability and offer an opportunity to explore the physical drivers of blocking behavior under both historical and future forcing scenarios.

4.2 Winter blocking in multidecadal simulations

In the previous section, short (5-year) simulations were analysed. They provide only limited information because they do not fully capture the inter-annual variability. In this section, we assess blocking frequency, duration, and size biases in multidecadal storm-resolving simulations (IFS amip, IFS hist, IFS SSP3-7.0, ICON hist, and ICON SSP3-7.0) and in the multi-model mean of eight CMIP6 models with respect to ERA5. We focus on the Northern Hemisphere winter (DJF) to identify the most significant and robust biases across models. Results for the Southern Hemisphere, as well as blocking frequency biases using the ABS index, are provided in the Appendix 7 and 8. The JJA season is discussed in the next section.

Figure 5 shows the DJF blocking differences to ERA5. The IFS simulation locally overestimates the blocking frequency, but the negative North Atlantic blocking bias that characterizes the CMIP6 ensemble mean is reduced (Figure 5 a and f). Nevertheless, biases remain in other regions, highlighting that while IFS mitigates some biases, it does not fully resolve blocking representation issues (Fig. 5a,b). ICON simulations substantially underestimate the blocking frequency over the Atlantic and the Pacific basin and exhibit an eastward shift in blocking patterns. Quantitatively, the ICON RMSE (1.89) is higher than that of CMIP6 (1.42) and IFS hist (1.21) in the North Atlantic (see Table 5). Among the IFS experiments, the atmosphere-only simulation (IFS amip) performs best. In the North Pacific, the coupled IFS simulations (IFS hist) tend to overestimate blocking frequency, while IFS amip shows reduced biases and better agreement with ERA5. ICON simulations underestimate blocking frequency over the Pacific and overestimate blocking activity over California, similar to the IFS amip.

We further analyze the number of blocking events per year in both the North Atlantic and North Pacific basins (Figs. 6a,d). In the North Atlantic, IFS AMIP and CMIP6 mean and median values are close to ERA5, while ICON and IFS hist underestimate the number of events. IFS amip again shows the best performance.

In the North Pacific, IFS simulations tend to underestimate the number of blocking events, whereas ICON simulations overestimate them. Interestingly, the CMIP6 ensemble mean shows the best agreement with ERA5, this could be due to a smoothing effect from averaging across models. Despite underestimating the blocking frequency, the IFS simulations outperform ICON, and notably, the coupled IFS runs perform better than the atmosphere-only configuration in this basin.

Figures 6b,e show the distribution of blocking durations. In the North Atlantic, IFS simulations tend to overestimate the average duration but capture the upper percentiles (95th) well, particularly in IFS amip and SSP3-7.0. ICON performs better in terms of mean duration, with ICON SSP3-7.0 outperforming the CMIP6 mean.

In the North Pacific, IFS historical and amip simulations produce both average and extreme durations longer than ERA5. Combined with the frequency overestimation (Figs. 5a,c) and the lower number of blocks (Figs. 6d), this indicates that fewer, longer-lasting blocks contribute to the overall frequency. ICON, conversely, produces more but shorter-lived blocks, consistent with its frequency underestimation and higher block count.

A key blocking characteristic is the blocking size, as larger blocks tend to have greater societal

impacts (e.g., Nabizadeh et al., 2019). In the North Atlantic, IFS simulations overestimate blocking size relative to ERA5. IFS amip generates the largest blocks on average and at the upper percentiles—this may explain local frequency overestimation, such as over the Iberian Peninsula (Fig. 5b). ICON simulations produce smaller blocks than ERA5, and their size distribution is similar to the CMIP6 ensemble mean.

In the North Pacific, IFS coupled simulations and the CMIP6 ensemble slightly overestimate blocking size. IFS amip simulates smaller blocks. ICON simulations also produce slightly smaller blocks, but again, results are close to the CMIP6 mean.

Our analysis highlights that storm-resolving climate models can offer advantages in simulating blocking characteristics, particularly in the North Atlantic during DJF:

- IFS performance is generally better than ICON across all blocking metrics.
- IFS amip consistently outperforms other simulations, especially in frequency and duration, indicating the critical role of accurate ocean surface forcing.
- In the North Pacific, coupled IFS runs perform better than the atmosphere-only configuration, despite some overestimation in duration and size.
- ICON simulations tend to underestimate frequency and duration but slightly outperform IFS in capturing realistic average durations.

These results support the use of storm-resolving simulations for improving the representation of atmospheric blocking when ocean-atmosphere interactions are well captured.

Figure 5: Blocking frequency biases against ERA5 during Northern Hemisphere winter (DJF), based on the ANOM index, for (a) IFS historical, (b) IFS atmosphere-only, (d) ICON historical, and (f) the CMIP6 ensemble mean. The SSP3-7 response (SSP3-7 minus historical) is shown for (c) IFS and (e) ICON. Black contours indicate ERA5 blocking frequency (4% intervals starting at 4%). Hatched areas highlight regions with relative differences exceeding 80%. Black dots indicate statistically significant differences (Z-test for storm-resolving models; model agreement $\geq 80\%$ for CMIP6). Blue and red dashed lines outline the North Atlantic and North Pacific basins, respectively.

Simulation	Atlantic RMSE	Pacific RMSE
IFS hist	1.21	1.20
IFS AMIP	1.06	1.04
ICON hist	1.89	1.53
CMIP6 ensemble	1.42	1.23

Table 5: Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of DJF blocking frequency in historical simulations relative to ERA5, separated for the North Atlantic and North Pacific sectors.

Figure 6: Number of blocking events and their properties in the (a,b,c) North Atlantic basin and (d,e,f) North Pacific basin. The extent of the basins is shown as dashed lines in Fig. 5, with blue representing the Atlantic and red the Pacific basin. Boxes represent the interquartile range (Q1–Q3), with the horizontal line indicating the median, whiskers extending from the 5th to the 95th percentile, and the red dot denoting the mean. Boxes with hatching indicate statistically significant differences relative to ERA5, based on a Mann-Whitney U test ($p < 0.05$).

4.2.1 The background flow

We first examine how biases in the background flow relate to winter blocking characteristics in the multidecadal storm-resolving simulations. Figure 7 shows the mean zonal wind at 500 hPa during DJF. In the IFS coupled simulation (hist), there is a 2 to 3 m/s positive bias of the zonal flow over the eastern North Atlantic and Europe and a positive bias along the northern edge of the jet over the North Pacific. The positive bias in the North Atlantic region coincides with a negative blocking frequency bias. The IFS simulations capture the overall spatial structure of the jet streams but with amplitude biases. IFS amip shows a more realistic jet strength and position, closer to ERA5. In the North Atlantic, the IFS-AMIP configuration shows a reduction in RMSE from 1.92 m/s (IFS-hist) to 0.88 m/s (IFS-AMIP) relative to ERA5 (Table 8). ICON simulations overestimate the jet strength in both the North Atlantic and North Pacific basins. This likely contributes to the underestimation of blocking frequency and the predominance of short-lived blocking events in the ICON simulations.

Figure 7: Mid-level (500 hPa) zonal wind difference to ERA5 in the Northern Hemisphere winter for (a) IFS historical, (b) IFS atmosphere-only, (d) ICON historical, and (f) the CMIP6 ensemble mean. The SSP3-7 response (SSP3-7 minus historical) is shown for (c) IFS and (e) ICON. The ERA5 zonal wind is indicated by contours. Hatched areas indicate regions where the bias relative to ERA5 exceeds 80%.

4.2.2 Representation of the ocean

In both seasons, the blocking frequency was better captured in the IFS amip simulations than in the coupled run. To investigate the influence of ocean variability on blocking, we compare the coupled IFS hist simulations with their atmosphere-only counterparts (IFS amip) and explore how SST anomalies are associated with the location and frequency of winter blocking. Additionally, we use ICON and CMIP6 simulations as references to contextualize the role of ocean forcing across different model frameworks. Note that the SST biases across the eight CMIP6 models used here is similar to those of all CMIP6 models and the CMIP5 models (Zhang et al., 2023).

As shown in Fig. 8, SST anomalies in the North Atlantic are closely linked to shifts in blocking maxima. In particular, negative SST anomalies in the subpolar gyre are associated with a reduced blocking frequency over the North Atlantic in the IFS hist simulations. This suggests an

Simulation	Atlantic RMSE (m/s)	Pacific RMSE (m/s)
IFS historical	1.92	2.61
IFS AMIP	0.88	0.99
ICON historical	3.50	5.65
MRI-ESM2-0	3.00	4.13
ACCESS-CM2	2.31	2.39
EC-Earth3	1.23	1.93
MPI-ESM1-2-HR	2.53	2.93
CESM2-WACCM	1.36	1.13
MIROC6	2.56	3.47
MPI-ESM1-2-LR	2.43	2.45
CESM2	1.63	1.35
CMIP6 ensemble mean	2.13	2.47

Table 6: Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of 500 hPa zonal wind relative to ERA5 for different historical simulations, computed over the Northern Hemisphere Atlantic and Pacific basins (DJF).

ocean–atmosphere coupling mechanism whereby enhanced meridional SST gradients might strengthen the lower-tropospheric baroclinicity, leading to an intensification of the eddy-driven jet and a concomitant suppression of blocking development (Cheung et al., 2023; Athanasiadis et al., 2022). Consistent with this interpretation, Scaife et al. (2011) demonstrated that cold SST biases in the subpolar gyre are systematically associated with negative blocking biases in climate models. Despite a slightly warmer subpolar gyre SST in ICON relative to IFS, blocking is underestimated, and the eddy-driven jet is overly strong. In the North Pacific, the IFS coupled simulations show higher SSTs relative to ERA5, particularly in midlatitude regions. These warm anomalies may enhance surface latent heat fluxes, invigorating baroclinic development and strengthening the eddy-driven jet, consistent with the jet bias and extended block durations observed in this region (Hermoso et al., 2024).

Figure 8: SST difference to ERA5 in the Northern Hemisphere winter for (a) IFS historical, (b) IFS atmosphere-only, (d) ICON historical, and (f) the CMIP6 ensemble mean. The SSP3-7 response (SSP3-7 minus historical) is shown for (c) IFS and (e) ICON. The ERA5 SST frequency is indicated by contours. Hatched areas indicate regions where the difference relative to ERA5 exceeds 80%.

4.2.3 Representation of the storm tracks

Figure 9 shows the storm track intensity during DJF. Compared to ERA5, the IFS hist simulation captures the main storm track branches over both the North Pacific and North Atlantic. In the Atlantic, IFS hist exhibits a stronger and more eastward-extended storm track. IFS hist coupled simulation exhibits an overly strong storm track over the Mediterranean, whereas the IFS AMIP simulation better reproduces storm track intensity in both the North Atlantic and Mediterranean basins. This supports previous findings that prescribing observed SSTs helps constrain jet intensity and improves the realism of eddy-driven variability in climate models. ICON simulations, in contrast, exhibit an overly zonal and eastward-shifted storm track in both basins. This behavior reflects the stronger jet discussed earlier. The CMIP6 ensemble mean displays weaker and more equatorward storm tracks than ERA5, especially in the Atlantic — a long-standing bias in lower-resolution models (Zappa et al., 2013; Harvey et al., 2020; Priestley et al., 2023). At storm-resolving resolution, stronger atmosphere–ocean coupling emerges as mesoscale SST features and frontal structures are better resolved (Wills et al., 2024). Consequently, SST bi-

ases over the Pacific and Atlantic basins may exert a stronger dynamical influence on the large-scale atmospheric flow in ICON compared to coarser-resolution models. We hypothesize that this enhanced coupling contributes to the intensified and overly zonal jets observed in ICON, highlighting the critical importance of accurately representing both atmospheric and oceanic processes when simulating extratropical variability.

Figure 9: Stormtracks difference to ERA5 in the Northern Hemisphere winter for (a) IFS historical, (b) IFS atmosphere-only, (d) ICON historical, and (f) the CMIP6 ensemble mean. The SSP3-7 response (SSP3-7 minus historical) is shown for (c) IFS and (e) ICON. The ERA5 stormtracks amplitude is indicated by contours. Hatched areas indicate regions where the relative difference to ERA5 exceeds 80%.

4.3 Summer blocking in multidecadal simulations

We focus now on the Northern Hemisphere summer (JJA) to identify the most robust and significant biases across models. Figure 10 shows JJA blocking biases across the different simulations. Overall, the IFS simulations overestimate blocking frequency in the North Atlantic compared to ERA5 and the CMIP6 ensemble mean. ICON simulations also underestimate blocking frequency in the North Atlantic, but differences relative to ERA5 are generally small and not statistically significant. ICON hist outperforms the CMIP6 ensemble mean in terms of blocking frequency, exhibiting a lower RMSE relative to ERA5 (0.96 vs. 1.40). Among the IFS experiments,

the atmosphere-only simulation (IFS amip) performs best. For instance, the strong overestimation of Greenland blocking in IFS hist (exceeding 80%) is largely absent in IFS amip, consistent with a reduced blocking bias shown by the ABS index (Fig. 18b). In the North Pacific, the IFS hist simulation underestimates the blocking frequency, while IFS amip performs better, matching the ERA5 more closely. ICON simulations, in contrast to the Atlantic pattern, overestimate blocking frequency at higher latitudes, resembling the CMIP6 ensemble mean bias.

We next evaluate the number of blocking events per year (Figs. 11a,d). In the North Atlantic, IFS simulations produce mean and median values close to ERA5. IFS hist shows the best overall agreement, this may partly result from an overestimation of blocking over Greenland. The next best performer is IFS amip. ICON simulations underestimate the number of events, consistent with the frequency bias discussed above.

In the North Pacific, IFS simulations generally underestimate the number of blocking events, except for IFS amip, which produces slightly more. ICON simulations overestimate the number of blocks, similar to their winter behavior. The CMIP6 ensemble mean underestimates block count in a manner comparable to the IFS coupled simulations.

Figures 11b,e show the statistics for the blocking duration. In the North Atlantic, IFS simulations slightly overestimate the median blocking duration, especially in IFS amip and SSP3-7.0. ICON performs better than IFS amip in terms of median duration, with ICON SSP3-7.0 showing a distribution closer to ERA5 than the CMIP6 mean. In the North Pacific, all storm-resolving simulations reproduce the ERA5 median duration, while CMIP6 shows a higher median. More substantial differences emerge in the distribution tails and mean values. IFS hist produces shorter-duration blocks, which, combined with the low number of events (Fig. 11d), leads to an overall underestimation of blocking frequency (Fig. 10a). The IFS SSP3-7.0 simulation produces longer-lasting blocks (both in mean and upper percentiles), but given the lower number of events (Fig. 11d), the resulting blocking frequency remains below ERA5 (Fig. 10c). IFS amip simulates durations closest to ERA5, suggesting that its slightly elevated blocking frequency may be due to a combination of more blocking events and larger block sizes. ICON produces similar durations to ERA5, thus, its frequency overestimation (Figs. 10d,e) likely results from an excess number of blocks (Fig. 11d).

In the North Atlantic, IFS amip and SSP3-7.0 overestimate block size, while IFS hist shows the best overall agreement with ERA5. Thus, in terms of median performance across number of blocks, duration, and size, IFS hist performs best for summer blocking in the North Atlantic. IFS amip produces the largest blocks on average, and when combined with its slightly longer-lived blocks, this may help offset its lower block count, contributing to the modest overestimation in blocking frequency (Fig. 10a). ICON simulations, similar to winter, produce smaller blocks than ERA5. Interestingly, the changes in block size and duration under climate change differ between IFS and ICON simulations, a point we discuss further in Section 4.4.

In the North Pacific, IFS coupled simulations reproduce block size better than IFS amip. Note that IFS amip simulates larger blocks, suggesting that block size may be a limitation in the otherwise strong performance of this configuration. ICON simulations also slightly overestimate size, with results comparable to the CMIP6 mean.

Similar to winter, our analysis highlights that storm-resolving climate models offer potential ad-

vantages in simulating blocking characteristics, particularly in the North Atlantic during JJA:

- IFS simulations, especially IFS amip, better capture blocking number, duration, and size compared to ICON and the CMIP6 ensemble in the North Atlantic. For blocking frequency, IFS amip achieves the lowest RMSE, whereas IFS hist is affected by an overestimation of Greenland blocking (Table 7).
- IFS amip provides the most balanced performance across metrics, with realistic blocking duration and size, and reduced biases over Greenland—highlighting the importance of accurate ocean boundary conditions in summer.
- IFS hist performs best in simulating the median blocking properties in the North Atlantic, though its higher Greenland blocking count contributes to a frequency overestimation.
- In the North Pacific, all storm-resolving models capture median block duration well, but IFS amip shows higher block count and slightly overestimated block size.
- ICON simulations underestimate blocking frequency in the North Atlantic but overestimate it in the North Pacific, consistent with winter patterns; durations are realistic, but block sizes remain slightly underestimated.
- The CMIP6 ensemble mean underestimates the number of blocking events and produces longer-lived blocks, confirming known biases in lower-resolution models.

Taken together, these results demonstrate a potential added value of storm-resolving models for representing summer blocking dynamics, and highlight the relevance of ocean–atmosphere coupling.

Figure 10: Blocking frequency biases against ERA5 during Northern Hemisphere summer (JJA), based on the ANOM index, for (a) IFS historical, (b) IFS atmosphere-only, (d) ICON historical, and (f) the CMIP6 ensemble mean. The SSP3-7 response (SSP3-7 minus historical) is shown for (c) IFS and (e) ICON. Black contours indicate ERA5 blocking frequency (4% intervals starting at 4%). Hatched areas highlight regions with relative differences exceeding 80%. Black dots indicate statistically significant differences (Z-test for storm-resolving models; model agreement $\geq 80\%$ for CMIP6). Blue and red dashed lines outline the North Atlantic and North Pacific basins, respectively.

Simulation	Atlantic RMSE	Pacific RMSE
IFS hist	0.62	0.58
IFS AMIP	0.42	0.58
ICON hist	0.33	0.51
CMIP6 ensemble	0.60	0.68

Table 7: Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of JJA blocking frequency in historical simulations relative to ERA5, separated for the North Atlantic and North Pacific sectors.

Figure 11: Number of blocking events and their properties in the (a,b,c) North Atlantic basin and (d,e,f) North Pacific basin. The extent of the basins is shown as dashed lines in Fig. 10, with blue representing the Atlantic and red the Pacific basin. Boxes represent the interquartile range (Q1–Q3), with the horizontal line indicating the median, whiskers extending from the 5th to the 95th percentile, and the red dot denoting the mean. Boxes with hatching indicate statistically significant differences relative to ERA5, based on a Mann-Whitney U test ($p < 0.05$).

4.3.1 The climatological background flow

In boreal summer (JJA), the climatological background flow differs markedly from winter, featuring generally weaker westerlies and a more zonally symmetric pattern across the midlatitudes. Figure 12 shows the composite 500 hPa zonal wind and its bias relative to ERA5 for each simulation. All storm-resolving simulations capture the overall weaker midlatitude jet during summer. However, differences to ERA5 remain. Over central Eurasia, both IFS and ICON tend to simulate stronger westerlies than observed, which may contribute to the underestimation of blocking frequency in this region. A similar underestimation of blocking over northern Central Asia, near the Kara Sea, is also found in the CMIP6 ensemble mean (Fig. 12f).

Conversely, in the North Atlantic sector, IFS hist shows a locally weaker zonal flow southwest of Greenland, which may favor the development of more persistent ridges. In contrast, ICON and IFS amip simulate stronger westerlies and a lower blocking frequency bias.

IFS hist exhibits broader jets with enhanced zonal wind over the western Atlantic and Pacific,

a bias also present, though generally more pronounced, in the CMIP6 models. In contrast, IFS amp shows a poleward-shifted jet structure, which aligns more closely with ERA5 and contributes to its improved performance in simulating blocking frequency and duration. ICON simulations, like in winter, feature a strong eddy-driven jet that is both too zonal and shifted poleward, particularly over the Pacific and Atlantic. The largest biases are centered over the Asian continent and the North Pacific, consistent with the model's underestimation of blocking over Eurasia and overestimation at higher latitudes in the Pacific.

Overall, these results highlight that while storm-resolving models improve aspects of the background flow in summer, important biases remain—particularly in jet strength and latitude that directly influence blocking occurrence and characteristics.

Figure 12: Mid-level (500 hPa) zonal wind difference to ERA5 in the Northern Hemisphere summer for (a) IFS historical, (b) IFS atmosphere-only, (d) ICON historical, and (f) the CMIP6 ensemble mean. The SSP3-7 response (SSP3-7 minus historical) is shown for (c) IFS and (e) ICON. The ERA5 zonal wind is indicated by contours. Hatched areas indicate regions where the bias relative to ERA5 exceeds 80%.

Simulation	Atlantic RMSE (m/s)	Pacific RMSE (m/s)
IFS historical	2.39	2.34
IFS AMIP	0.99	1.38
ICON historical	2.06	2.90
MRI-ESM2-0	1.63	1.47
ACCESS-CM2	2.25	2.22
EC-Earth3	1.55	1.88
MPI-ESM1-2-HR	1.53	1.51
CESM2-WACCM	1.54	1.71
MIROC6	2.11	1.57
MPI-ESM1-2-LR	1.92	1.79
CESM2	1.40	1.75
CMIP6 ensemble mean	1.74	1.73

Table 8: Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of 500 hPa zonal wind relative to ERA5 for different historical simulations, computed over the Northern Hemisphere Atlantic and Pacific basins (JJA).

4.3.2 The ocean

In summer, the role of ocean variability in modulating atmospheric blocking differs from winter due to generally weaker ocean–atmosphere coupling (e.g., Barsugli and Battisti, 1998; Kushnir et al., 2002). However, despite the overall weaker coupling, sea surface temperature (SST) anomalies can still exert a strong influence on the background flow and on blocking development (e.g., Shaw and Voigt, 2015; Coumou et al., 2018). This is particularly relevant for our results, where differences between the IFS amip and IFS hist simulations highlight the importance of accurate SST boundary conditions for simulating summer blocking frequency.

Figure 13 shows the SST biases in JJA. In the North Atlantic, cold SST anomalies are associated with increased blocking south of Greenland. This relationship points to a potential feedback in which negative SST anomalies reduce surface heat fluxes, weaken the eddy-driven jet, and enhance the persistence of high-pressure systems (Häkkinen et al., 2011). The IFS coupled simulations generally exhibit cooler SSTs in the North Atlantic, particularly IFS hist, which shows the coldest anomalies. These SST biases are absent in IFS amip, which relies on prescribed SSTs. The fact that IFS amip reduces the blocking overestimation seen in IFS hist strongly supports the interpretation that ocean conditions, particularly the negative SST anomalies, play a critical role in modulating blocking frequency (Häkkinen et al., 2011; Hermoso et al., 2024).

In contrast, ICON simulations display positive SSTs biases in the North Atlantic, which likely enhance surface latent heat fluxes. This additional heating can invigorate the eddy-driven jet, leading to reduced blocking persistence and blocking frequency.

In the North Pacific, IFS hist also shows lower SSTs compared to ERA5, which may contribute to downstream jet development and, indirectly, to enhanced blocking over the North Atlantic. This connection is supported by the IFS SSP3-7.0 simulation, which lacks the same cold Pacific anomalies and exhibits a reduced number of Greenland blocking events compared to IFS hist. ICON, again, displays positive SST anomalies and a stronger Pacific oceanic front across the basin, reinforcing the earlier conclusion that warm SSTs contribute to jet intensification and reduced blocking through enhanced eddy activity (Cheung et al., 2023; Hermoso et al., 2024).

Taken together, these results emphasize that SST anomalies are a key factor in shaping summer blocking characteristics. Accurate representation of ocean conditions, either through realistic coupling or prescribed SSTs, are essential for capturing the background flow and jet strength, and by extension, blocking frequency and persistence in both seasons. These results also highlight the challenges in this new generation of SRM to reduce systematic biases that influence ocean-atmosphere coupling with implications on the atmospheric variability.

Figure 13: SST difference to ERA5 in the Northern Hemisphere summer for (a) IFS historical, (b) IFS atmosphere-only, (d) ICON historical, and (f) the CMIP6 ensemble mean. The SSP3-7 response (SSP3-7 minus historical) is shown for (c) IFS and (e) ICON. The ERA5 SST is indicated by contours. Hatched areas indicate regions where the bias relative to ERA5 exceeds 80%.

4.3.3 Storm tracks

Figure 14 illustrates the storm track intensity during boreal summer (JJA). As expected, storm-track activity is generally weaker and more confined to higher latitudes compared to winter, reflecting the reduced baroclinicity and weaker jet stream in summer (Zappa et al., 2013; Priestley et al., 2023). In the North Atlantic, the IFS coupled simulations (IFS hist) show storm tracks that extend eastward relative to ERA5. IFS amp exhibits the most realistic storm track structure, especially over the Atlantic basin. It shows better agreement with ERA5 in terms of both location and intensity and outperforms the CMIP6 ensemble, particularly by reducing storm-track intensity over the Asian continent. This improved performance is consistent with the better simulation of blocking frequency in IFS amp. ICON simulations show a relatively weak storm track over the North Atlantic. In the North Pacific, all simulations display either weaker or broader storm-track patterns compared to ERA5. This feature may help explain the overestimation of blocking frequency in ICON and CMIP6 models in the higher latitudes of the Pacific sector. The broader storm track structure may favor the formation of short-lived ridge anomalies that exceed

the blocking threshold.

These results emphasize that while summer storm tracks are weaker than in winter, their structure and intensity still influence the occurrence and characteristics of blocking. Storm-resolving models—especially IFS amp—demonstrate improved storm-track representation, which contributes to a more realistic simulation of summer blocking dynamics. Building on this evaluation of present-day conditions, we now turn to future projections to assess how blocking and storm-track behavior may evolve under continued climate change.

Figure 14: Stormtrack difference to ERA5 in the Northern Hemisphere summer for (a) IFS historical, (b) IFS atmosphere-only, (d) ICON historical, and (f) the CMIP6 ensemble mean. The SSP3-7 response (SSP3-7 minus historical) is shown for (c) IFS and (e) ICON. The ERA5 stormtracks amplitude is indicated by contours. Hatched areas indicate regions where the relative difference to ERA5 exceeds 80%.

4.4 Climate change insights

After evaluating present-day blocking biases, we next examine projected changes under future climate conditions. Specifically, we analyze the SSP3-7.0 simulations to explore how blocking frequency and properties may evolve in response to anthropogenic forcing, with a focus on seasonal and regional variations.

Figures 5 and 10 show projected changes in blocking frequency for DJF and JJA. During DJF, both IFS and ICON simulations show a reduction in blocking frequency at higher latitudes, particularly over Greenland and the North Atlantic, consistent with previous studies (Woollings et al., 2018). Concurrently, an increase in blocking frequency is projected at lower latitudes, suggesting a poleward contraction of the blocking activity zone.

In JJA the patterns differ IFS simulations project an increase in blocking frequency at higher latitudes (e.g., Greenland and northern Europe) and a decrease at lower latitudes (e.g., southern Europe). ICON shows a qualitatively similar but weaker response. These patterns suggest seasonally distinct mechanisms modulating blocking under climate change.

Beyond frequency changes, we also assess how blocking duration, size, and intensity respond to future warming. Projected changes in jet structure are relatively small in the SSP3-7.0 simulations (Figs. 7 and 12), with only modest shifts in zonal wind strength and latitude. Accordingly, the dynamical properties of blocks — including their duration and size — remain broadly similar to present-day conditions, with no major shifts evident in the overall distribution of blocking events (Figs. 6 and 11).

A closer examination, however, reveals model-dependent differences in how blocking properties respond to climate change. In IFS simulations, blocks tend to become slightly larger and longer-lived under SSP3-7.0, especially during summer, consistent with the projected increases in blocking frequency at higher latitudes. In contrast, ICON simulations project smaller and shorter-lived blocks compared to their present-day counterparts. IFS and ICON do not everywhere agree on how blocking characteristics will evolve, potentially reflecting differences in model physics, the different SST evolutions discussed in the previous section, resolution effects, or their treatment of moist processes and boundary-layer dynamics under warming conditions.

These contrasting responses highlight that, beyond changes in frequency, climate change may also affect the structure and lifetime of blocking events, with outcomes differing across model frameworks. Future studies will be needed to further explore the physical drivers of these differences.

Overall, these results suggest that climate change leads to a redistribution of blocking activity, with reduced high-latitude blocking in winter and increased high-latitude blocking in summer in IFS simulations. The small changes in jet characteristics might imply that thermodynamic processes such as Arctic amplification and surface forcing anomalies may play an increasingly important role in modulating future blocking patterns. These projected changes in blocking characteristics and their model dependencies motivate a broader discussion of the underlying physical mechanisms and potential implications for future climate variability.

5 Discussion

Our results suggest that increasing horizontal resolution can improve the simulation of atmospheric blocking in particular given the correct coupling to the ocean. The storm-resolving IFS and ICON simulations regionally capture the spatial structure, frequency, and persistence of blocking events more realistically compared to coarser CMIP6 models. Improvements are par-

ticularly evident in block size and duration during boreal winter (DJF), although in some cases individual CMIP6 models perform comparable to IFS or ICON. These improvements can be attributed to the enhanced ability of high-resolution models to resolve synoptic-scale features, including sharper gradients in geopotential height and more accurate jet stream structures, which has been suggested in idealized simulations (Schemm, 2023; De Luca et al., 2024) and the finest resolution of CMIP experiments (Schiemann et al., 2017; Schiemann et al., 2020; Gao et al., 2025).

Both IFS and ICON storm-resolving simulations outperform the CMIP6 ensemble mean in several key aspects:

- Better representation of block size and persistence, which are crucial for capturing the societal impacts of blocking.
- Improved blocking frequency patterns in some regions like the North Atlantic and North Pacific.
- Stronger large-scale atmosphere–ocean coupling, which is weaker or absent in simulations with coarser resolution (Wills et al., 2024).

Another important improvement offered by storm-resolving simulations is the strengthening of large-scale atmosphere–ocean coupling. In coarser CMIP6 models, this coupling is often underestimated because mesoscale oceanic fronts and eddies, which strongly influence air–sea heat fluxes and the structure of the lower atmosphere, are not adequately resolved (Wills et al., 2024). By better representing these mesoscale features, IFS and ICON simulations allow for a more realistic exchange of heat and momentum between the ocean and atmosphere, potentially affecting jet dynamics and blocking development. These improvements are particularly relevant in oceanic regions like the North Atlantic and North Pacific, where surface boundary conditions play a critical role in shaping midlatitude circulation.

Blocking frequency is closely tied to the structure of the midlatitude jet stream. Our simulations show that stronger, zonally aligned jets are associated with reduced blocking development, while weaker or more meridionally aligned jets are associated with more frequent persistent high-pressure anomalies. Storm-resolving models, particularly IFS amp, reproduce the jet's location more accurately than CMIP6, though intensity biases remain. These jet biases, especially over the North Atlantic and North Pacific, may help explain many of the regional blocking anomalies. ICON displays a too strong and poleward eddy-driven jet ("hyperactive jet") in both basins. Despite a poleward bias in jet position, ICON underestimates blocking frequency, likely because its intensified and overly zonal jets inhibit the amplification and persistence of large-scale Rossby wave patterns necessary for blocking development.

One of the most robust findings is the central role of SSTs and ocean–atmosphere coupling in shaping blocking behavior. IFS amp, which uses prescribed observed SSTs, consistently outperforms its coupled counterpart (IFS hist) in simulating blocking frequency and duration, particularly over Greenland and the North Pacific. In summer (JJA), cold SST biases in IFS hist are associated with weaker surface latent heat fluxes and modified surface temperature gradients, potentially reducing baroclinicity and favoring more persistent blocking events (Athanasiadis et al., 2022; Hermoso et al., 2024). However, the relationship between latent heat fluxes and

blocking is complex, as enhanced latent heating could also support stronger Warm Conveyor Belt activity and promote ridge amplification (Steinfeld and Pfahl, 2019; Steinfeld et al., 2020). In winter (DJF), the presence of stronger meridional SST gradients may instead support the formation of blocking by enhancing baroclinicity and promoting jet distortions. Conversely, warm SST anomalies in ICON enhance surface heating, strengthen the jet, and reduce blocking persistence (Wills et al., 2024). Furthermore, a remote influence of the Pacific oceanic front appears crucial for blocking variability, as described by Cheung et al., 2023.

These findings emphasize that realistic SST patterns and absolute SSTs, including those linked to the Atlantic Multidecadal Variability (AMV) and Pacific SST gradients, are essential for good blocking simulations. Accurate ocean boundary conditions are thus a prerequisite for realistic large-scale circulation in storm-resolving climate models.

Storm-track intensity and location are closely associated with blocking behavior. Shifts in storm-track structure can influence the jet and create conditions that are more or less favorable for the development of blocking anticyclones. Moreover, storm tracks and blocking can interact in both directions, as blocking anticyclones can also deflect storm tracks and modify their intensity and position. IFS amip again shows better agreement with ERA5 in storm-track structure and intensity, particularly over the Atlantic basin, while CMIP6 tend to simulate overly zonal and equatorward-shifted storm tracks. Interestingly, a weaker storm track does not necessarily lead to more blocking, as seen in ICON's summer simulations. This behavior is consistent with the findings of Hassanzadeh et al. (2014), who emphasized that reduced transient eddy activity can promote blocking only if the background flow conditions are favorable. This highlights the complex interaction between transient eddies, jet structure, and meridional thermal gradients. Storm tracks influence blocking, but their effect is strongly mediated by the background flow characteristics (e.g., Zappa et al., 2014; Brayshaw et al., 2008).

Despite the progress offered by higher resolution and improved SST representation, some blocking biases remain. One likely source of these biases is the representation of moist processes—particularly warm conveyor belts (WCBs), latent heat release, and diabatic heating (Dolores-Tesillos et al., 2025). Diabatic heating associated with WCBs plays a critical role in ridge amplification, modifies potential vorticity structures, and can precondition the flow for blocking onset (e.g., Pfahl et al., 2015; Dolores-Tesillos et al., 2025). Inaccurate simulation of these moist processes may thus contribute to biases in block persistence and amplitude. Future work should investigate the moist dynamics of blocking in storm-resolving models in more detail, including the role of cloud–radiative interactions, the vertical structure of diabatic heating, and the role of convection parametrizations.

Storm-resolving simulations offer a promising path forward for improving the realism of persistent weather regimes. Better blocking representation improves seasonal prediction, climate change assessments, and risk estimates for high-impact weather events.

To build on these advances, future research should focus on:

- Continued development and evaluation of coupled storm-resolving Earth system models.
- Improved parameterizations of moist processes and their interaction with large-scale dynamics.

- Targeted diagnostics of moist processes associated with WCBs and diabatic heating.
- Systematic evaluation of stormtrack–blocking coupling and SST–jet interactions.
- Targeted sensitivity experiments with perturbed SSTs could help disentangle the relative roles of oceanic and atmospheric processes in driving jet biases at storm-resolving resolution.

Beyond evaluating present-day biases, our results also provide important insights into projected changes in blocking behavior under future climate scenarios. Our analysis of SSP3-7.0 simulations provides new insights into how blocking may evolve under future warming. Storm-resolving models project a spatial redistribution of blocking activity, with reduced high-latitude blocking in winter and increased high-latitude blocking in summer, particularly in IFS simulations. However, substantial model differences remain, especially regarding blocking persistence and size, highlighting ongoing uncertainties linked to background flow changes, SST anomalies, and moist processes under warming. These results underscore the importance of improving blocking representation in current models to enhance confidence in future projections of persistent weather extremes. Storm-resolving modeling offers a promising path toward a more accurate simulation of blocking and persistent extremes. Future efforts must prioritize high resolution, realistic surface forcing, and improved physical process representation to meet the challenges of a changing climate.

6 Conclusions

This study assesses the representation of atmospheric blocking in storm-resolving climate simulations from the nextGEMS project, comparing them with ERA5 and the CMIP6 multi-model ensemble. We focus on blocking frequency, duration, and size during both boreal winter (DJF) and summer (JJA) in the Northern Hemisphere. Simulations include coupled and atmosphere-only experiments with IFS and ICON, enabling evaluation of the effects of resolution, ocean forcing, and large-scale dynamics.

Our key findings are as follows:

- **Resolution matters:** storm-resolving amip simulations outperform CMIP6 models in blocking frequency, duration, and spatial structure, particularly in the North Atlantic. Higher resolution improves the simulation of synoptic-scale features, including jet structure and block size.
- **IFS outperforms ICON:** Among the models evaluated, IFS simulations consistently show better agreement with ERA5. ICON simulations tend to produce stronger, zonally aligned jets and underestimate blocking frequency, particularly in the North Atlantic.
- **Jet and storm-track dynamics influence blocking:** Blocking frequency and persistence are closely tied to the strength and structure of the midlatitude jet and associated storm tracks.
- **Moist processes remain a source of bias:** Despite improvements, some blocking bi-

ases persist. These may be linked to unresolved or poorly represented moist processes, including warm conveyor belts, latent heating, and diabatic feedbacks.

- **Future projections are enabled:** The inclusion of SSP3-7.0 scenario simulations provides a first step toward assessing future blocking behavior. Storm-resolving models project a redistribution of blocking activity under warming, although persistent biases highlight the need for continued refinement of storm-resolving coupled models.

Overall, our results highlight the potential of high spatial resolution, accurate ocean boundary conditions, and improved process representation for realistic simulation of atmospheric blocking. Storm-resolving models like those from the nextGEMS project represent a significant advance over traditional GCMs and offer a promising pathway for future climate modeling efforts.

Further work should focus on diagnosing moist processes and their impact on blocking, improvements in blocking structure, extending storm-resolving evaluation to other seasons and regions, and developing targeted improvements in coupled model physics to address remaining biases.

7 Appendix: SH blocking frequency with ANO index

Figure 15: Blocking frequency biases against ERA5 during Southern Hemisphere summer (DJF), based on the ANOM index, for (a) IFS historical, (b) IFS atmosphere-only, (d) ICON historical, and (f) the CMIP6 ensemble mean. The SSP3-7 response (SSP3-7 minus historical) is shown for (c) IFS and (e) ICON. Black contours indicate ERA5 blocking frequency (4% intervals starting at 4%). Hatched areas highlight regions with relative differences exceeding 80%. Black dots indicate statistically significant differences (Z-test for storm-resolving models; model agreement $\geq 80\%$ for CMIP6). Blue and red dashed lines outline the North Atlantic and North Pacific basins, respectively.

Figure 16: Blocking frequency biases against ERA5 during Southern Hemisphere winter (JJA), based on the ANOM index, for (a) IFS historical, (b) IFS atmosphere-only, (d) ICON historical, and (f) the CMIP6 ensemble mean. The SSP3-7 response (SSP3-7 minus historical) is shown for (c) IFS and (e) ICON. Black contours indicate ERA5 blocking frequency (4% intervals starting at 4%). Hatched areas highlight regions with relative differences exceeding 80%. Black dots indicate statistically significant differences (Z-test for storm-resolving models; model agreement $\geq 80\%$ for CMIP6). Blue and red dashed lines outline the North Atlantic and North Pacific basins, respectively.

8 Appendix: NH blocking frequency with ABS index

Figure 17: Blocking frequency biases against ERA5 during Northern Hemisphere winter (DJF), based on the ABS index, for (a) IFS historical, (b) IFS atmosphere-only, (d) ICON historical, and (f) the CMIP6 ensemble mean. The SSP3-7 response (SSP3-7 minus historical) is shown for (c) IFS and (e) ICON. The ERA5 blocking frequency is indicated by contours. Hatched areas indicate regions where the bias relative to ERA5 exceeds 80%.

Figure 18: Blocking frequency biases against ERA5 during Northern Hemisphere winter (DJF), based on the ABS index, for (a) IFS historical, (b) IFS atmosphere-only, (d) ICON historical, and (f) the CMIP6 ensemble mean. The SSP3-7 response (SSP3-7 minus historical) is shown for (c) IFS and (e) ICON. The ERA5 blocking frequency is indicated by contours. Hatched areas indicate regions where the bias relative to ERA5 exceeds 80%.

9 Appendix: Zonal mean wind against latitude in the North Atlantic and North Pacific

Figure 19: Mid-tropospheric (500 hPa) zonal mean zonal wind (m s^{-1}) against latitude for the North Atlantic and North Pacific basins during winter (DJF), for the different historical simulations. Vertical lines indicate the latitude of jet maxima.

Figure 20: Mid-tropospheric (500 hPa) zonal mean zonal wind (m s^{-1}) against latitude for the North Atlantic and North Pacific basins during summer (JJA), for the different historical simulations. Vertical lines indicate the latitude of jet maxima.

10 References

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